

Defining clinical diagnosis and treatment of puerperal metritis in dairy cows: A Scoping Review.

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Supplemental Table S2. Risk of bias assessment of the included studies on the treatment of cows with metritis (n=32). Green/ L letter indicates items that were judged low ROB. Yellow/question mark indicates items that were judged unclear ROB. Red/H letter indicates items that were judged high ROB.

Study	Disease definition	Randomization	Baseline characteristics	Blinding of personnel	Blinding outcome	Incomplete outcome data	Selective outcome reporting	others
Jeon et al., 2018	H	L	H	?	L	L	L	L
Lomb et al., 2018	L	L	L	L	L	?	?	L
Freick et al., 2018	?	L	L	H	H	?	?	L
Newby et al., 2017	H	L	?	L	?	L	?	L
Daetz et al., 2016	L	L	L	H	L	L	L	L
Freick et al., 2017	H	L	?	H	H	L	L	L
Pinedo et al., 2017	L	L	L	H	H	L	L	L
Jeon et al., 2016	H	L	H	H	H	?	?	L
Piccardi et al., 2016	H	H	H	H	H	L	?	L
Pohl et al., 2016	L	L	L	?	H	H	L	L
Cui et al., 2015	L	L	H	H	L	?	L	?
Burfeind et al., 2014	L	H	?	H	?	L	L	?
Jeremejeva et al., 2015	?	L	?	?	?	L	L	L
Lima et al., 2014	L	L	L	H	H	L	L	L
Pinedo et al., 2015	?	L	?	L	L	L	L	L
Armegol et al., 2015	?	H	?	H	H	?	?	L
McLaughlin et al., 2012	?	H	?	L	L	?	?	?
Bhat et al., 2012	H	L	H	H	?	?	?	?
Sannmann et al., 2013	L	L	?	H	H	L	L	?
McLaughlin et al., 2013	?	L	?	L	L	L	L	L
Giuliodori et al., 2012	H	L	H	H	H	?	?	?
Galvao et al., 2009	H	L	L	?	?	?	L	L
Goshen et al., 2006	?	L	?	?	?	?	L	?
Dolezel et al., 2008	?	L	?	H	H	?	?	?
Chenault et al., 2004	L	L	L	L	L	L	L	L
Melendez et al., 2004	H	?	?	H	H	?	L	L
Drillich et al., 2001	?	H	?	H	H	L	L	?
Smith et al., 2002	?	L	?	?	?	?	L	L
Amiridis et al., 2001	?	L	?	?	?	?	?	?
Pohl et al., 2016	L	L	L	?	H	H	L	L
Jeremejeva et al., 2012	?	L	L	H	H	L	?	?
Sannmann et al., 2014	L	L	L	H	H	L	L	L